

QUASI γ -NORMAL SPACES IN TOPOLOGICAL SPACES

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we introduce the concept of $\pi\gamma$ -closed sets as weak form of π g-closed sets. We also introduce the notion of quasi γ -normal spaces and by using $\pi\gamma$ -closed sets, we obtain a characterization and preservation theorems for quasi γ -normal spaces. Further we show that this property is a topological property and it is a hereditary property only with respect to closed domain subspaces. The relationships among normal, π -normal, quasi-normal, mildly-normal, p-normal, π p-normal, quasi p-normal, mildly p-normal, γ -normal, $\pi\gamma$ -normal, quasi γ -normal, mildly γ -normal are investigated.

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I INTRODUCTION

The notion of quasi normal space was introduced by Zaitsev [14]. Levine [6] initiated the investigation of g-closed sets in topological spaces. Singal and Singal [11] introduced the notion of mildly normal spaces which are weaker than quasi-normal spaces. Nour [9] introduced the notion of p-normal spaces and obtained their properties. Lal and Rahman [5] have further studied notions of quasi normal and mildly normal spaces. Dontchev and Noiri [1] introduced the notion of π g-closed sets as a weak form of g-closed sets due to Levine [6]. By using π g-closed sets, Dontchev and Noiri [1] obtained a new characterization of quasi normal spaces. Kalantan [4] introduced a weaker version of normality called π -normality and proved that π -normality is a property which lies between normality and almost normality. Ekici [2] introduced a new class of normal spaces, called γ -normal spaces and the relationships among s-normal, p-normal and γ -normal spaces are investigated. Thabit and Kamarulhaili [13] introduced a weaker version of p-normality called π p-normality, which lies between p-normality and almost p-normality. Recently, Thabit and Kamarulhaili [12] introduced a weaker form of p-normality called quasi p-normality, which lies between π p-normality and mild p-normality.

II PRELIMINARIES

Throughout this paper, spaces (X, τ) , (Y, σ) , and (Z, γ) (or simply X , Y and Z) always mean topological spaces on which no separation axioms are assumed unless explicitly stated. Let A be a subset of a space X . The closure of A and interior of A are denoted by $\text{cl}(A)$ and $\text{int}(A)$ respectively. A subset A is said to be **regular open** (resp. **regular closed**) if $A = \text{int}(\text{cl}(A))$ (resp. $A = \text{cl}(\text{int}(A))$). The finite union of regular open sets is said to be **π -open**. The complement of a π -open set is said to be **π -closed**. A subset A is said to be **γ -open** [3] if $A \subset \text{cl}(\text{int}(A)) \cup \text{int}(\text{cl}(A))$. The complement of a γ -open set is said to be **γ -closed** [3]. The intersection of all γ -closed sets containing A is called **γ -closure** [3] of A , and is denoted by $\gamma\text{cl}(A)$. The **γ -interior** [3] of A , denoted by $\gamma\text{int}(A)$, is defined as union of all γ -open sets contained in A .

2.1 Definition. A subset A of a space X is said to be

- (1) **generalized closed** (briefly **g-closed**) [6] if $\text{cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \tau$.
- (2) **π g-closed** [1] if $\text{cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is π -open in X .
- (3) **generalized γ -closed** [2] if $\gamma\text{cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \tau$.
- (4) **π g γ -closed** if $\gamma\text{cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is π -open in X .
- (5) **g-open** (resp. **π g-open**, **g γ -open**, **π g γ -open**) if the complement of A is g-closed (resp. π g-closed, g γ -closed, π g γ -closed).

III QUASI γ -NORMAL SPACES

3.1 Definition. A space X is said to be **γ -normal** [2] (resp. **p-normal** [9, 10]) if for every pair of disjoint closed subsets A, B of X , there exist disjoint γ -open (resp. p-open) sets U, V of X such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$.

3.2 Definition. A space X is said to be **π g-normal** (resp. **π -normal** [4], **π p-normal** [13]) if for every pair of disjoint closed subsets A, B of X , one of which is π -closed, there exist disjoint γ -open (resp. open, p-open) sets U, V of X such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$.

3.3 Definition. A space X is said to be **quasi γ -normal** (resp. **quasi-normal** [14], **quasi p-normal** [12]) if for every pair of disjoint π -closed subsets H, K of X , there exist disjoint γ -open (resp. open, p-open) sets U, V of X such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$.

3.4 Definition. A space X is said to be **mildly γ -normal** (resp. **mildly-normal** [11], **mildly p-normal** [7]) if for every pair of disjoint regular closed subsets H, K of X , there exist disjoint γ -open (resp. open, p-open) sets U, V of X such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$.

By the definitions stated above, we have the following diagram:

Where none of the implications is reversible as can be seen from the following examples:

3.5 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, X\}$. Then the space X is π p-normal as well as $\pi\gamma$ -normal but not p-normal.

3.6 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Then the space X is p-normal as well as π p-normal.

3.7 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, X\}$. Then the space X is γ -normal as well as $\pi\gamma$ -normal but not p-normal.

3.8 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{b, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{b, c, d\}, X\}$. Then the space X is γ -normal but not normal.

3.9 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{b, c, d\}, X\}$. The pair of disjoint closed subsets of X are $A = \{a\}$ and $B = \{c\}$. Also $U = \{a, b\}$ and $V = \{c, d\}$ are p-open sets such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$. Hence the space X is p-normal as well as γ -normal but not normal.

3.10. Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d, e\}$ and $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{e\}, \{a, b\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, e\}, \{c, d, e\}, \{a, b, c, d\}, X\}$. The pair of disjoint π -closed subsets of X are $A = \{a, b\}$ and $B = \{c, d\}$. Also $U = \{a, b, e\}$ and $V = \{c, d\}$ are γ -open sets such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$. Hence the space X is quasi γ -normal but not quasi normal, since U and V are not open sets.

3.11. Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d, e\}$ and $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c, d, e\}, \{b, c, d, e\}, X\}$. The pair of disjoint π -closed subsets of X are $A = \{a\}$ and $B = \{b\}$. Also $U = \{a, c\}$ and $V = \{b, d\}$ are p-open sets such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$. Hence the space X is quasi p-normal as well as quasi γ -normal but not quasi normal, since U and V are not open sets.

3.12 Theorem. For a space X , the following are equivalent:

- (a) X is quasi γ -normal.
- (b) For every pair of π -open subsets U and V of X whose union is X , there exist γ -closed subsets G and H of X such that $G \subset U$, $H \subset V$ and $G \cup H = X$.

(c) For any π -closed set A and every π -open set B in X such that $A \subset B$, there exists a γ -open subset U of X such that $A \subset U \subset \gamma\text{cl}(U) \subset B$.

(d) For every pair of disjoint π -closed subsets A and B of X , there exist γ -open subsets U and V of X such that $A \subset U$, $B \subset V$ and $\gamma\text{cl}(U) \cap \gamma\text{cl}(V) = \emptyset$.

Proof. (a) \Rightarrow (b), (b) \Rightarrow (c), (c) \Rightarrow (d) and (d) \Rightarrow (a).

(a) \Rightarrow (b). Let U and V be any π -open subsets of a quasi γ -normal space X such that $U \cup V = X$. Then, $X - U$ and $X - V$ are disjoint π -closed subsets of X . By quasi γ -normality of X , there exist disjoint γ -open subsets U_1 and V_1 of X such that $X - U \subset U_1$ and $X - V \subset V_1$. Let $G = X - U_1$ and $H = X - V_1$. Then, G and H are γ -closed subsets of X such that $G \subset U$, $H \subset V$ and $G \cup H = X$.

(b) \Rightarrow (c). Let A be a π -closed and B is a π -open subsets of X such that $A \subset B$. Then, $X - A$ and B are π -open subsets of X such that $(X - A) \cup B = X$. Then, by part (b), there exist γ -closed sets G and H of X such that $G \subset (X - A)$, $H \subset B$ and $G \cup H = X$. Then, $A \subset (X - G)$, $(X - B) \subset (X - H)$ and $(X - G) \cap (X - H) = \emptyset$. Let $U = X - G$ and $V = (X - H)$. Then U and V are disjoint γ -open sets such that $A \subset U \subset X - V \subset B$. Since $X - V$ is γ -closed, then we have $\gamma\text{cl}(U) \subset (X - V)$. Thus, $A \subset U \subset \gamma\text{cl}(U) \subset B$.

(c) \Rightarrow (d). Let A and B be any disjoint π -closed subset of X . Then $A \subset X - B$, where $X - B$ is π -open. By the part (c), there exists a γ -open subset U of X such that $A \subset U \subset \gamma\text{cl}(U) \subset X - B$. Let $V = X - \gamma\text{cl}(U)$. Then, V is a γ -open subset of X . Thus, we obtain $A \subset U$, $B \subset V$ and $\gamma\text{cl}(U) \cap \gamma\text{cl}(V) = \emptyset$.

(d) \Rightarrow (a). It is obvious.

3.13 Proposition. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be a function, then:

- (a) The image of γ -open subset under an open continuous function is γ -open.
- (b) The inverse image of γ -open (resp. γ -closed) subset under an open continuous function is γ -open (resp. γ -closed) subset.
- (c) The image of γ -closed subset under an open and a closed continuous surjective function is γ -open.

3.14 Theorem. The image of a quasi γ -normal space under an open continuous injective function is a quasi γ -normal.

Proof. Let X be a quasi γ -normal space and let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be an open continuous injective function. We need to show that $f(X)$ is a quasi γ -normal. Let A and B be any two disjoint π -closed sets in $f(X)$. Since the inverse image of a π -closed set under an open continuous function is a π -closed. Then, $f^{-1}(A)$ and $f^{-1}(B)$ are disjoint π -closed sets in X . By quasi γ -normality of X , there exist γ -open subsets U and V of X such that $f^{-1}(A) \subset U$, $f^{-1}(B) \subset V$ and $U \cap V = \emptyset$. Since f is an open continuous injective

function, we have $A \subset f(U)$, $B \subset f(V)$ and $f(U) \cap f(V) = \emptyset$. By **Proposition 3.13**, we obtain $f(U)$ and $f(V)$ are disjoint γ -open sets in $f(X)$ such that $A \subset f(U)$ and $B \subset f(V)$. Hence $f(X)$ is quasi γ -normal.

From the above theorem, we have the following corollary.

3.15 Corollary. Quasi γ -normality is a topological property.

The following lemma helps us to show that quasi γ -normality is a hereditary with respect to closed domain subspaces.

3.16 Lemma. Let M be a closed domain subspace of a space X . If A is a γ -open set in X , then $A \cap M$ is γ -open set in M .

3.17 Theorem. Quasi γ -normality is a hereditary with respect to closed domain subspaces.

Proof. Let M be a closed domain subspace of a quasi γ -normal space X . Let A and B be any disjoint π -closed sets in M . Since M is a closed domain subspace of X , then we have A and B be any disjoint π -closed sets of X . By quasi γ -normality of X , there exist disjoint γ -open subsets U and V of X such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$. By the **Lemma 3.16**, we obtain $U \cap M$ and $V \cap M$ are disjoint γ -open sets in M such that $A \subset U \cap M$ and $B \subset V \cap M$. Hence, M is quasi γ -normal subspace.

IV PRESERVATION THEOREMS

The following result is useful for giving some other characterizations of quasi γ -normal spaces.

4.1 Lemma. A subset A of a space X is $\pi\gamma$ -open if and only if $F \subset \gamma \text{int}(A)$ whenever $F \subset A$ and F is π -closed.

4.2 Theorem. For a space X , the following are equivalent:

- (a) X is quasi γ -normal.
- (b) For any disjoint π -closed sets H and K , there exist disjoint $\gamma\pi$ -open sets U and V such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$
- (c) For any disjoint π -closed sets H and K , there exist disjoint $\pi\gamma$ -open sets U and V such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$.
- (d) For any π -closed set H and any π -open set V containing H , there exists a $\gamma\pi$ -open set U of X such that $H \subset U \subset \gamma \text{cl}(U) \subset V$.
- (e) For any π -closed set H and any π -open set V containing H , there exists a $\pi\gamma$ -open set U of X such that $H \subset U \subset \gamma \text{cl}(U) \subset V$.

Proof. (a) \Rightarrow (b), (b) \Rightarrow (c), (c) \Rightarrow (d), (d) \Rightarrow (e) and (e) \Rightarrow (a).

(a) \Rightarrow (b). Let X be quasi γ -normal space. Let H, K be disjoint π -closed sets of X . By assumption, there exist disjoint γ -open sets U, V such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$. Since every γ -open set is $g\gamma$ -open, so U and V are $g\gamma$ -open sets such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$.

(b) \Rightarrow (c). Let H, K be two disjoint π -closed sets. By assumption, there exist disjoint $g\gamma$ -open sets U and V such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$. Since $g\gamma$ -open set is $\pi g\gamma$ -open, so U and V are $\pi g\gamma$ -open sets such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$.

(c) \Rightarrow (d). Let H be any π -closed set and V be any π -open set containing H . By assumption, there exist disjoint $\pi g\gamma$ -open sets U and W such that $H \subset U$ and $X - V \subset W$. By **Lemma 4.1**, we get $X - V \subset \gamma \text{int}(W)$ and $\gamma \text{cl}(U) \cap \gamma \text{int}(W) = \emptyset$. Hence $H \subset U \subset \gamma \text{cl}(U) \subset X - \gamma \text{int}(W) \subset V$.

(d) \Rightarrow (e). Let H be any π -closed set and V be any π -open set containing H . By assumption, there exist $g\gamma$ -open set U of X such that $H \subset U \subset \gamma \text{cl}(U) \subset V$. Since, every $g\gamma$ -open set is $\pi g\gamma$ -open, there exists $\pi g\gamma$ -open sets U of X such that $H \subset U \subset \gamma \text{cl}(U) \subset V$.

(e) \Rightarrow (a). Let H, K be any two disjoint π -closed sets of X . Then $H \subset X - K$ and $X - K$ is π -open. By assumption, there exists $\pi g\gamma$ -open set G of X such that $H \subset G \subset \gamma \text{cl}(G) \subset X - K$. Put $U = \gamma \text{int}(G)$, $V = X - \gamma \text{cl}(G)$. Then U and V are disjoint γ -open sets of X such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$.

4.3 Definition. A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be

- (a) **γ -closed [2]** (resp. **$\pi g\gamma$ -closed**) if $f(F)$ is γ -closed (resp. $\pi g\gamma$ -closed) in Y for every closed set F of X .
- (b) **rc-preserving [8]** (resp. **almost closed [11], almost γ -closed, almost $\pi g\gamma$ -closed**) if $f(F)$ is regular closed (resp. closed, γ -closed, $\pi g\gamma$ -closed) in Y for every $F \in RC(X)$.
- (c) **π -continuous [1]** (resp. **almost π -continuous [1]**) if $f^{-1}(F)$ is π -closed in X for every closed (resp. regular closed) set F of Y .
- (d) **almost continuous [11]** if $f^{-1}(V)$ is open in X for every regular open set V of Y .
- (e) **$\pi g\gamma$ -continuous** (resp. **almost $\pi g\gamma$ -continuous**) if $f^{-1}(F)$ is $\pi g\gamma$ -closed in X for every closed (resp. regular closed) set F of Y .

4.4 Theorem. If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is an almost π -continuous and $\pi g\gamma$ -closed function, then $f(A)$ is $\pi g\gamma$ -closed in Y for every $\pi g\gamma$ -closed set A of X .

Proof. Let A be any $\pi g\gamma$ -closed set of X and V be any π -open set of Y containing $f(A)$. Since f is almost π -continuous, $f^{-1}(V)$ is π -open in X and $A \subset f^{-1}(V)$. Therefore, we have $\gamma \text{cl}(A) \subset f^{-1}(V)$ and hence $f(\gamma \text{cl}(A)) \subset V$. Since f is $\pi g\gamma$ -closed, $f(\gamma \text{cl}(A))$ is $\pi g\gamma$ -closed in Y and hence we obtain $\gamma \text{cl}(f(A)) \subset \gamma \text{cl}(f(\gamma \text{cl}(A))) \subset V$. Hence $f(A)$ is $\pi g\gamma$ -closed in Y .

4.5 Theorem. A surjection $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is almost $\pi\gamma$ -closed if and only if for each subset S of Y and each $U \in RO(X)$ containing $f^{-1}(S)$, there exists a $\pi\gamma$ -open set V of Y such that $S \subset V$ and $f^{-1}(V) \subset U$.

Proof. Necessity. Suppose that f is almost $\pi\gamma$ -closed. Let S be a subset of Y and $U \in RO(X)$ containing $f^{-1}(S)$. If $V = Y - f(X - U)$, then V is a $\pi\gamma$ -open set of Y such that $S \subset V$ and $f^{-1}(V) \subset U$.

Sufficiency. Let F be any regular closed set of X . Then $f^{-1}(Y - f(F)) \subset (X - F)$ and $(X - F) \in RO(X)$. There exists a $\pi\gamma$ -open set V of Y such that $Y - f(F) \subset V$ and $f^{-1}(V) \subset (X - F)$. Therefore, we have $f(F) \supset (Y - V)$ and $F \subset X - f^{-1}(V) \subset f^{-1}(Y - V)$. Hence we obtain $f(F) = Y - V$ and $f(F)$ is $\pi\gamma$ -closed in Y , which shows that f is almost $\pi\gamma$ -closed.

4.6 Theorem. If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is an almost $\pi\gamma$ -continuous, rc-preserving injection and Y is quasi γ -normal then X is quasi γ -normal.

Proof. Let A and B be any disjoint π -closed sets of X . Since f is an rc-preserving injection, $f(A)$ and $f(B)$ are disjoint π -closed sets of Y . Since Y is quasi γ -normal, there exist disjoint γ -open sets U and V of Y such that $f(A) \subset U$ and $f(B) \subset V$.

Now if $G = \text{int}(\text{cl}(U))$ and $H = \text{int}(\text{cl}(V))$. Then G and H are regular open sets such that $f(A) \subset G$ and $f(B) \subset H$. Since f is almost $\pi\gamma$ -continuous, $f^{-1}(G)$ and $f^{-1}(H)$ are disjoint $\pi\gamma$ -open sets containing A and B which shows that X is quasi γ -normal.

4.7 Theorem. If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is π -continuous, almost γ -closed surjection and X is quasi γ -normal space then Y is γ -normal .

Proof. Let A and B be any two disjoint closed sets of Y . Then $f^{-1}(A)$ and $f^{-1}(B)$ are disjoint π -closed sets of X . Since X is quasi γ -normal, there exist disjoint γ -open sets U and V such that $f^{-1}(A) \subset U$ and $f^{-1}(B) \subset V$.

Let $G = \text{int}(\text{cl}(U))$ and $H = \text{int}(\text{cl}(V))$. Then G and H are disjoint regular open sets of X such that $f^{-1}(A) \subset G$ and $f^{-1}(B) \subset H$. Now, we set $K = Y - f(X - G)$ and $L = Y - f(X - H)$. Then K and L are γ -open sets of Y such that $A \subset K, B \subset L, f^{-1}(K) \subset G$ and $f^{-1}(L) \subset H$. Since G and H are disjoint, K and L are disjoint. Since K and L are γ -open and we obtain $A \subset \gamma\text{int}(K), B \subset \gamma\text{int}(L)$ and $\gamma\text{int}(K) \cap \gamma\text{int}(L) = \emptyset$. Therefore, Y is γ -normal.

4.8 Theorem. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be an almost π -continuous and almost $\pi\gamma$ -closed surjection. If X is quasi γ -normal space then Y is quasi γ -normal.

Proof. Let A and B be any disjoint π -closed sets of Y . Since f is almost π -continuous, $f^{-1}(A)$ and $f^{-1}(B)$ are disjoint π -closed sets of X . Since X is quasi γ -normal, there exist disjoint γ -open sets U and V of X such that $f^{-1}(A) \subset U$ and $f^{-1}(B) \subset V$.

Put $G = \text{int}(\text{cl}(U))$ and $H = \text{int}(\text{cl}(V))$. Then G and H are disjoint regular open sets of X such that $f^{-1}(A) \subset G$ and $f^{-1}(B) \subset H$. By **Theorem 4.5**, there exist γ -open sets K and L of Y such that $A \subset K$, $B \subset L$, $f^{-1}(K) \subset G$ and $f^{-1}(L) \subset H$. Since G and H are disjoint, so are K and L by **Lemma 4.1**, $A \subset \gamma\text{int}(K)$, $B \subset \gamma\text{int}(L)$ and $\gamma\text{int}(K) \cap \gamma\text{int}(L) = \emptyset$. Therefore, Y is quasi γ -normal.

4.9 Corollary. If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is an almost continuous and almost closed surjection and X is a normal space, then Y is quasi γ -normal.

Proof. Since every almost closed function is almost $\pi\gamma$ -closed by **Theorem 4.8**, Y is quasi γ -normal.

V CONCLUSION

We introduced a weaker version of γ -normality called quasi γ -normality. We proved that it is a topological property and a hereditary property with respect to closed domain subspaces. We gave some characterizations and preservation theorems of quasi γ -normal spaces. Some counterexamples were given and some basic properties were presented. The relationships among normal, π -normal, quasi-normal, mild-normality, p -normal, πp -normal, quasi p -normal, mild p -normal, γ -normal, $\pi\gamma$ -normal, quasi γ -normal, mild γ -normal are investigated.

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